

Towards a more sustainable supply of critical raw materials: the role of prospective Life Cycle Assessment

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Development in the Minerals Industry*

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METALLICO: Overview

METALLICO project will contribute to unlock substantial reserves of currently unexploited and underexploited resources within the EU by demonstrating at TRL6-7 innovative technologies to produce battery metals from primary and secondary sources

In particular, **METALLICO** will:

- Recover valuable materials from unexploited primary and secondary resources
- Demonstrate sustainable production and recovery of (critical) battery metals
- Assess end-use of the recovered (critical) battery metals

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METALLICO: Processes

LITHIUM IBERIA
(Spain)

COBRE LAS CRUCES
(Spain)

KHGM
(Poland)

THARSIS MINING
(Spain)

COOL+

TAILCO

PURGES

CONI

COMAN

Low concentration
Lithium-containing ores

Tailings from Cu
hydrometallurgical processing

Purges from polymetallurgical
refining processes

Waste alloys generated in lead
hydrometallurgical processing

Tailings from sulfuric
acid production

Li

Co

Co Cu

Co Cu Ni

Co Cu Ni Mn

METALLICO: Processes

LITHIUM IBERIA
(Spain)

COOL+

Low concentration
Lithium-containing ores

Li

The processes have been demonstrated at lab scale (M18) and will be soon optimized and then upscaled to pilot (M44)

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Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA)

A pLCA studies a technology at an early phase of development projecting its potential environmental impacts to a potential future industrial scale.

Adapted from: Van Nielen et al. (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142453>
 (TRL: technology readiness level; MRL: manufacturing readiness level; MPL: market penetration level)

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Prospective Life Cycle Assessment (pLCA)

A pLCA studies a technology at an early phase of development projecting its potential environmental impacts to a potential future industrial scale.

Its main objective is to identify potential environmental hotspots and the most sustainable design choices. Its results can provide valuable information to steer process development towards a more sustainable direction.

Case study: TAILCO process

TAILCO aims at treating **tailings** originated in Cu hydrometallurgical processes to recover:

- A **metallic cobalt cement** that will be used in battery cathodes manufacturing
- **H₂SO₄** that will be internally recycled in hydrometallurgical processes
- A **Zinc concentrate** to achieve a zero-waste process

Challenges of pLCA: data upscaling

Lab scale

Iron removal		
Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Metal concentrate after nanofiltration	x	kg
Chemical 1	x	kg
Chemical 2	x	kg
Coagulants	x	kg
Electricity	?	kWh
Outputs	Quantity	Unit
Cobalt-rich solution	1	kg
Iron sludge	x	kg

x	Measured at lab scale and needs to be upscaled to industrial scale
?	Generally not measured at lab scale and needs to be estimated for industrial applications

Challenges of pLCA: data upscaling

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Industrial scale

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Challenges of pLCA: data upscaling

Lab scale

?

Industrial scale

Possible approaches:

- Scaling relationships + proxies + expert judgements
- Process simulation

Challenges of pLCA: development scenarios

Lab scale

Multiple potential
development scenarios

Industrial scale

Challenges of pLCA: development scenarios

Lab scale

Multiple potential
development scenarios

Industrial scale

Scenarios should explore:

- Different process configurations
- Different chemical agents
- Different process yields or operating parameters
- Different circularity solutions

pLCA as a tool for process engineers

The goal is to use the results of the pLCAs to steer the development of METALLICO processes towards a more sustainable direction.

Di Maria et al. (2024)

Metals recovery and residues valorization
Sulfidic tailings in Sweden

Adrianto & Pfister (2022)

Metals recovery only
Sulfidic tailings from Cu-Zn deposit in Portugal

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METALLICO – Partners

DECHEMA
Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.V.

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Fraunhofer IKTS

NIKKELVERK
A GLENCORE COMPANY

VTT

idener SCIENTIFIC COMPUTING

THARSIS MINING

UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA BARCELONATECH

CETAQUA WATER TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

CIC energigUNE MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

EuroAtomizado Grupo

CEMENTOS CRUZ

CLAVE

CLC

Łukasiewicz
Instytut Metali Nieżelaznych

Politecnico di Torino

CETAQUA CHILE

BARBOT

LARCO

21 PARTNERS

9 COUNTRIES

5 INNOVATIVE PROCESSES

Thanks for your attention

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